

FUNCTIONAL LINKAGE BETWEEN WAREHOUSE AND TRANSPORT PROCESSES IN DOOR-TO-DOOR CARGO DELIVERY

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ABSTRACT

This article is based on the implementation of the “door-to-door” cargo transportation principle. The operation of the traditional cargo delivery chain is based on the direct cooperation between warehouse and transportation processes. This cooperation forms a unified logistics process scheme for the movement of material flows from the dispatch point to the final consumer. In the cargo delivery system, warehouse and transportation processes are not considered as separate elements, but rather as interrelated and complementary functional components that ensure the continuity and regularity of logistics processes.

Introduction. The functional interdependence of warehouse and transport processes reflects the technological process at all stages of material flow movement, starting from the arrival of cargo at the warehouse and ending with its delivery to the consumer.

Regardless of whether transportation is international or domestic, in all transport operations where a change of transport mode occurs, different types of warehouses are used depending on the nature of the cargo. In cargo transportation performed exclusively by road transport over relatively short distances (500–700 km), the use of transshipment warehouses may not be required; however, even in this transport scheme, warehouses are still used at the initial and final points of delivery. In all other transport schemes, which constitute the majority of cargo transportation, transshipment operations involving changes in transport modes are performed.

Based on their functional role, warehouses perform operations such as receiving cargo (material flows), loading and unloading, sorting and placement, long-term storage, temporary storage, and forming orders as material flow units.

Considering the above, the efficient organization of the technological workflow of warehouses directly involved in cargo transportation is of significant importance. Proper organization of warehouse technological operations enables a reduction in excessive cargo dwell time in warehouses, a decrease in cargo processing time, and a reduction in the operational costs of transport equipment used within warehouses.

An efficient organization of warehouse technological processes not only affects warehouse operations but also influences the overall cargo delivery process, contributing to a reduction in logistics costs and delivery times. In the cargo delivery chain, coordination and effective management of each link in the transportation process are essential.

During periods of increased transportation volumes, each link in the system has its own maximum cargo handling capacity. The maximum processing capacity of warehouses depends on several key parameters. These parameters include the type of cargo being handled, warehouse overall dimensions relative to warehouse type, storage duration, operational technology, loading and unloading equipment, and proper workflow planning.

In logistics systems, the main factors (objective functions) of cargo transportation are reducing logistics costs, minimizing delivery time, and ensuring a high level of cargo safety. Achieving these objectives requires the comprehensive organization, monitoring, and management of the cargo delivery process based on the “door-to-door” principle.

In this context, it is necessary to analyze the operational principles of each link in the transportation process in order to identify the “weakest point” or multiple “weak points” within the transport chain. The identified weak points should be eliminated through the implementation of modern, scientifically based approaches.

In logistics supply chains, without identifying the weakest link in cargo transportation, achieving the set objectives becomes almost impossible.

Transportation using multiple modes of transport results in a multi-stage transport process consisting of several interconnected links.**

Q_i - Throughput or cargo handling capacity of a specific link in door-to-door material flow delivery.

$$q_{\min} = \min\{Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, \dots, Q_i\}, \quad i = 1; n \quad [1]$$

$$q_{\max} = \max\{Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, \dots, Q_i\}, \quad i = 1; n \quad [2]$$

q_{\min} - weakest link in the cargo transportation system.

q_{\max} - the link with the highest cargo throughput or processing capacity in the transportation system

$$q_{\min} \lambda q_{\max} \quad [3]$$

λ - coefficient of cargo flow irregularity

Using Formula [3], the objective is to increase the capacity of the “weakest” link in the cargo transportation system by accounting for the potential future growth of material flow and the cargo flow irregularity coefficient, and to align it with the throughput capacity of the “best” (highest-capacity) link within the system.

Research shows that in cargo transportation systems, particularly when using multiple modes of transport, the “weakest link” is typically warehouses (intermodal cooperation points). Taking these factors into account, it is of significant importance to determine and substantiate the optimal values of the technical and technological parameters of warehouses within the cargo transportation system.

q_{\min} - The warehouse processing capacity is defined, and the following parameters are determined.

$$q_{\min} = Q_{\text{ombor}} = \frac{S_f H_f \gamma}{T}, t / sut \quad [4]$$

The warehouse processing capacity is directly proportional to volumetric density and inversely proportional to the average storage time of cargo in the warehouse. In addition to

these technical parameters, technological factors are also of significant importance, including loading and unloading equipment and the efficient organization of warehouse technological operations.

In the process of “door-to-door” cargo delivery, the identified “weak point,” namely the warehouse, is influenced by various technical and technological factors affecting its operational performance and development parameters. These key parameters are presented in Figure 1 using an Ishikawa diagram.

The Ishikawa diagram is a cause-and-effect analysis tool used to study and analyze the relationship between existing problems and their consequences in a given situation. This diagram allows for the identification of both positive and negative factors, as well as primary and secondary influencing factors affecting warehouse technical and technological processes, thereby enabling an accurate assessment of the system.

Figure 1. Factors affecting warehouse processing capacity

The identified diagram indicates the need to develop scientifically grounded recommendations aimed at increasing the implementation level of the most significant positive influencing factors, as well as reducing the impact of negative influencing factors.

Conclusion. As a result of the study, the effective organization of warehouse technology is of great importance for the "door-to-door" delivery of goods, primarily through cargo reloading and reloading. The processing capacity of the warehouse is directly proportional to the bulk density and inversely proportional to the average storage period of the cargo in the warehouse. Along with these technical parameters, their significance depends on technological factors, namely the effective organization of the technological workflow of loading and unloading machines and the warehouse.

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